

The Horizontal-to-Vertical Spectral Ratio Method for Underground Voids Detection: Testing Over Mycenaean Tombs

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Abstract

This study investigates the potential of the Horizontal-to-Vertical (H/V) spectral ratio method, a technique typically used for site characterization, as a complementary tool for detecting underground voids. We leverage ambient noise measurements conducted at the Mycenaean cemetery of Voudeni, Peloponnese, Greece, utilizing the site's numerous underground tombs as test targets. We analyzed the H/V spectral amplitudes above the centers of various sized tombs and the spatial variation of horizontal and vertical spectral amplitudes and of their ratio along trial linear arrays. We verify the suggestion of previous research that over voids the H/V curve shows a characteristic drop below unity at high frequencies (in our test cases, typically >20Hz), which remains below unity for a considerable frequency interval. This phenomenon is attributed to a velocity reversal caused by the void within the surrounding rock. We attempt a first-order comparison of the void size and frequency of initiation of the characteristic drop and conclude that larger subsurface voids tend to affect the H/V curve at lower frequencies compared to smaller voids, exhibiting an exponential relationship. We also observe that the H/V drop over our test voids is primarily driven by the amplification of the vertical component rather than de-amplification of the horizontal component and this suggests that using linear arrays of vertical component geophones alone could be effective for void detection, particularly as a complement to other geophysical methods. We demonstrate this possibility through trial linear arrays of vertical sensors. We conclude that the H/V method and linear arrays of vertical sensors hinder promising advancements as void detection techniques, especially considering their readily deployable and cost-effective character, although theoretical modeling and extensive testing in various geological settings and void characteristics are required to better understand the observed phenomena.

Background and Objective

The Horizontal to Vertical Spectral Ratio (H/V or HVSR) method (Nogoshi and Igarashi, 1971; Nakamura, 1989) involves the analysis of earthquakes or microtremor (ambient noise) records to compute the ratio of the spectral amplitudes of the horizontal components to the vertical component. It was originally proposed as a method to calculate the local amplification and resonance frequency resulting from sedimentary layers overlying the bedrock. For the simplified case of a viscoelastic sedimentary soil layer of thickness h and shear wave velocity V_s , over a viscoelastic bedrock, the resonance frequency f_n is calculated by the formula:

$$f_n = (2n + 1) \frac{V_s}{4h}, (n = 0, 1, 2, \dots)$$

Empirical data have shown that the lowest frequency at which the maximum value of the H/V curve is observed at a site, is identical or very close to the resonance frequency, f_0 , of the soil by shear waves SH. In addition to f_0 , the method can provide information on the thickness of the soil over bedrock, the presence of high density layers, lateral discontinuities of the subsoil layers from variations of the curves at different locations and velocity reversals (e.g. from natural or artificial hard layer over softer soil) (e.g., Field and Jacob 1993; Lermo and Chávez-García 1994a; Bonilla et al. 1997; Bour et al. 1998; Bard 1998; Fäh et al. 2001; Woolery and Street 2002; Molnar and Cassidy 2006; Haghshenas et al. 2008).

As the popularity of the H/V method increases, several aspects of its practical application are being examined in more detail. One such aspect involves the performance of the method at sites where there is a strong velocity reversal very close to the ground surface. This situation often arises when measurements are collected on top of concrete slabs, asphalt, etc, as discussed in detail in Castellaro and Mulargia (2009). A special case falling under this category is the presence of underground voids close to the surface, either natural or man-made (e.g., cellars, underground parking spaces). Castellaro and Mulargia (2009) present H/V curves for several example cases and discuss that under the absence of shallow velocity reversals, the common plot of the spectra of the horizontal and vertical components presents a characteristic oval shape around f_0 , what the authors describe as 'eye shape'. According to the same study, the appearance of this feature suggests that the H/V peak is of stratigraphic origin. Also, when there are no velocity reversals the vertical component remains less than or equal to the horizontal component at all frequencies, hence $H/V \geq 1$, except for a small range near $2 \times f_0$ where it can drop below unity due to the elliptical motion of Rayleigh waves (Fäh et al., 2001). In contrast, if the amplitudes of the H/V curve fall below 1 in regions distant from $2 \times f_0$ and remain below 1 for a considerable range of frequencies, this may be evidence for a velocity reversal.

In this work, we further investigate the suggestion of Castellaro and Mulargia (2009) that the H/V curve over voids is expected to show characteristic drops below unity. More generally, we examine the working hypothesis that the method could be useful, at least as a complementary method, in the detection of underground voids. For this purpose, we have chosen as test site the Mycenaean cemetery of Voudeni in the Peloponnese, ~4 km east-northeast of the city of Patras. The archaeological site contains

numerous underground tombs that the Mycenaeans constructed more than 3000 years ago by carving into the soft rock (marl) of the area. Many tombs of different sizes and depths have been excavated and their geometry has been studied in detail by Turner (2020), making them ideal targets for our study.

Our study included three phases of ambient noise data collection and processing, which will be presented sequentially in the following. Data collection was conducted during daylight hours and when the archaeological site was not in operation to minimize nearby anthropogenic noise.

Three-Component Single-Point Ambient Noise Measurements Over Voids of Various Dimensions

In the first phase of our study, we performed single-point H/V measurements over several tombs of different dimensions targeting to 1) identify a characteristic imprint of voids on the shape of the H/V curves, as suggested by previous researchers, and 2) identify a possible correlation between the dimensions of the voids on the characteristics of this imprint. Data were collected using a Geometrics Atom-3C seismic acquisition unit with a 2Hz, three-component (3C) geophone and sampling rate of 4 ms (Nyquist frequency of 125 Hz). The sensor was placed over the centers of several ancient burial chambers, i.e. our target underground cavities, it was oriented to the North and was left to record ambient noise for at least 15 minutes. Since all targets are located at shallow depths (<1m to a maximum of 7-8m), longer recordings were not considered necessary.

Figure 1 shows an example measurement setting. The upper part of the Figure contains the plan view of a measured tomb (a; circled in red) and the side view of its detailed reconstruction (b; wireframe from photogrammetry) by Turner (2020). The lower part of Figure 1 (c-d) contains photographs of the tomb. In general, Mycenaean tombs include an entrance passage or “dromos”, a threshold or “stomion”, and the burial chamber/vault or “thalamos”. The facets of excavated tombs extend from the stomion floor to the ground, and we used them as reference planes to measure the distance to the center of the void chamber, first underground and then on the ground surface.

Figure 1. Example measurement setting: a) tomb (circled in red) ground plan and b) side view of its textured photogrammetric model by Turner (2020), c) photograph of the entrance pathway (dromos), d) photograph from the inside of the tomb (thalamos) looking at the stomion and e) photograph of the Atom-3C on the ground surface, over the void chamber.

Although our test site includes 78 excavated burial monuments, we were only able to measure 24, mostly because many chamber tops collapsed over the years or access to their tops was dangerous. Some geometric characteristics of these tombs, as provided by Turner (2020), are summarized in Table 1. The difference between the height of the dromos and the height of the vault is often a good proxy for the depth of the vault top.

The collected data were processed using using SPACPlus module of the SeisImager-sw software from Geometrics Inc. (<https://www.geometrics.com/software/seisimager-sw/>). Ambient noise time histories were trimmed at the beginning and end of each measurement to remove noise during instrument installation and removal. The common recording for the three components was then divided into segments of 512 samples, i.e. ~ 2 s duration, with an overlap of 50%. Fourier amplitude spectra were computed for each component and each recording segment, and the horizontal component spectra were geometrically averaged. Finally, the H/V ratio was computed for each segment and the results were visually inspected (both in terms of H/V curve shape and directly on the ambient noise records) to remove irregularly noisy segments and spectra. The remaining measurements were used to derive the mean H/V curve for each measured location.

Table 1. Geometric characteristics of the 24 Mycenaean tombs (after Turner, 2020, except those with * vault volume measured in the frame of this study) over which we performed ambient noise measurements.

Tomb Code	Vault Volume (m ³)	Dromos Height (m)	Vault Length (m)	Vault Width (m)	Vault Height (m)	Tomb Code	Vault Volume (m ³)	Dromos Height (m)	Vault Length (m)	Vault Width (m)	Vault Height (m)
01	20.63	2.33	2.47	2.94	2.05	34	32.9	3.16	3.16	3.09	2.33
02	17.42	2.36	2.2	4.04	1.83	42	18.7	2.11	2.48	2.66	1.71
06	16.98	2.24	2.16	2.51	1.76	43*	13.1	-	2.8	2.6	2.5
07	47.03	3.47	3.21	1.11	1.14	53	65.5	4.34	3.57	3.71	2.79
08	21.9	2.84	2.79	2.73	1.79	54	81.4	5.09	3.15	4.55	2.87
09	27.3	2.71	3.01	2.96	2.4	55	-	3.89	-	-	-
16	11.14	2.37	1.96	2.82	1.36	60	18.9	2.61	2.69	2.62	1.96
22	42.6	4.5	3.37	3.36	2.91	64	40	2.85	3.25	3.27	2.41
23*	20.4	-	2.3	2.3	1.8	71	28.3	3.64	3.18	3.15	2.7
25	126.3	4.29	4.79	3.9	4.09	72	17.11	2.92	2.63	2.71	2.21
28	13.49	2.21	2.39	2.65	1.96	75	257	6.6	5.08	7.6	4.57
29	82.1	3.93	3.66	4.7	3.29	78	106	5.47	3.8	4.58	3.23

Figure 2a shows an example output for the measurement over tomb 78 (Table 1). In the upper part of Figure 2a, the horizontal and vertical component spectra are compared, and it is clearly seen that, for a significantly wide range of frequencies (~22-38Hz), the vertical spectral amplitudes are larger than the horizontal, i.e., opposite to what is usually expected. This results in a drop of the H/V curve in the corresponding frequency range, as shown in the lower part of Figure 2a. The H/V returns to amplitude >1 at frequencies ~>35Hz.

Figure 2. a) Example results of the H/V analysis of data over tomb 78. Upper part: Fourier amplitude spectra (FAS) of the horizontal and vertical components (in blue and red, respectively). The circled area is where the vertical component spectral amplitudes appear larger than the horizontal. Lower part: H/V spectral ratio. The circle marks the characteristic drop of the H/V ratio below unity, at high frequencies and for a significantly wide range. b) Underground void volume (in m³) with respect to f_{DL} the frequency of initiation of the persistent H/V drop below 1Hz.

We define f_{DL} as the frequency above which we observe a sustained drop in H/V amplitude below 1, and we examined whether this discrete frequency is related to the volume of the underground void. The corresponding plot is shown in Figure 2b and implies an exponential relationship between the compared quantities, i.e. as the void volume increases, the frequency where H/V first drops below 1, in a clear and systematic manner, shifts to lower frequencies. This suggests that larger subsurface voids, at least at the shallow depths investigated here, affect the H/V curve at lower frequencies compared to smaller voids. However, this relationship appears to saturate (flattens) as void volumes become smaller (~<20-30m³). A similar examination with respect to the depth of the tomb ceilings did not provide evidence for a clear relation, most probably because most ceilings are at very shallow depths of 0.5-1.5m and their geometry varies.

Three-Component Linear Array Ambient Noise Measurements Over a Large Void

One question raised by the previous measurements is how the persistent H/V drop varies spatially, and whether an underground void can be detected even if the ambient noise measurement is not taken directly over its center. Therefore, in the second part of our study, we collected data along a line over one example tomb to investigate, to some extent, the spatial variability of the shape of the H/V curve over a void. The test was conducted on tomb 75, which is the largest of the tombs examined in terms of volume (Table 1). The measurements were made in a linear arrangement across the center of the tomb. The total number of measuring

points was 13, with 2 m between successive measurements. The first was placed 6 m from the north side of the chamber and the last 10 m from the south side (Figure 3a, b).

Examples of results for two of the 13 sites are shown in Figure 3c, d. Specifically, results are shown for location S6, just above the center of the tomb (Figure 3c), and for S12, 5-6 m south of the tomb (Figure 3d). Focusing on the high frequency part of the results, the differences are quite pronounced with a very wide H/V drop below unity at S6 and a flat H/V curve around 1 at S12. Looking at the corresponding results for all 13 sites (not all are shown for reasons of space), the drop of the H/V curve below 1 clearly occurs at sites S4, S5, S6, S7, and S8 (Figure 3b), while at the remaining sites either no drop below 1 or drops within quite short ranges are observed.

Figure 3. Linear array of 3C measurement points over one of the largest tombs (codenamed 75) in the Mycenaean Park of Voudeni a) in plan view and b) in cross section (depth and volume not to scale); c) Results for the example locations S6 right over the tomb and d) for S12, several meters to the south of the tomb. Top panels in c, d show the Fourier amplitude spectra of the horizontal and the vertical components and bottom panels the H/V curves.

From plots such as those in Figure 3c, d, it is difficult to understand the spatial variability of the results and even more difficult to understand whether the H/V drop is mostly due to de-amplification of the horizontal signal or amplification of the vertical signal. To better demonstrate the spatial variability of our results, we created spectrogram-like plot, but instead of time in the horizontal axis, we plotted the distance of each spectrum or H/V curve from S1. This creates a pseudo-2d spatial variation, which we show in Figure 4 in separate subplots for the amplitudes of the horizontal and vertical Fourier spectra and the H/V curve. The subplots for the horizontal and vertical components (Figure 4a, b) have the same color scale and are directly comparable. Note that since the horizontal axis shows the distance from S1, the measurements directly above the tomb are in the range of 6-14 m. This exact range is clearly colored differently in the H/V subplot (cool colors, mostly <1), starting from frequencies close to 20 Hz and continuing to much higher frequencies. This means that the changes in the wavefield due to the underground void are clearly imprinted on the spatial variability of the H/V amplitudes at high frequencies over the entire structure and not just over its center. In fact, the lateral extent of the structure is well captured in this subplot. By examining the individual component plots, we conclude that the H/V variation is mostly due to a corresponding spatial variation in the vertical component amplitudes (circled areas in Figure 4b). This means that the H/V drop over the studied underground void is mostly due to an increase of the vertical component amplitudes at high frequencies rather than a decrease of the horizontal component spectral amplitudes in the same range.

Figure 4. Pseudo-2D plot of results (spectral amplitudes or amplitude ratio vs distance from the starting measurement in the linear array) over tomb 75 for a) the horizontal Fourier amplitude spectra, b) the vertical Fourier amplitude spectra and c) the H/V amplitude. In the central plot for the vertical component, two prominent areas of spectral amplitude amplification are circled.

Vertical Component Linear Array Measurements Over Selected Voids

The preceding results indicated that it is possible to detect the presence of underground voids just by using the vertical component of ambient noise measurements. We further examined this potential by conducting measurements along a second linear array above two adjacent, smaller tombs. In this third phase of our work, we used 6 2Hz, 1-component geophones (Atom-1C, Geometrics), spaced every 1m along a line crossing over the chambers of tombs 28 and 29 (Table 1, Figure 5). The chambers of these two tombs are right next to each other and their separating “wall” was so thin that a small part collapsed, partly joining the two void spaces. It should also be noted that the chamber of tomb 29 is about 6-7 times larger in volume than the chamber of tomb 28 and that their floor depths differ by ~1.5m (Table 1). Fourier amplitude spectra for each recording were computed following the same processing steps as before and plotted against distance. The exact geometry and location of the linear array and the pseudo-2D variation of spectral amplitudes are shown in Figure 5. Distances are measured from geophone A1 (Figure 5a, b). At high frequencies (i.e., >~20Hz) in Figure 5b, we can clearly observe higher spectral amplitudes at distances corresponding to the locations of geophones A1 and A3-A5. A1 was placed exactly over the centre of tomb 28, whereas A3-A5 were over the chamber of tomb 29. A2 and A6 are close to the boundaries of the voids and although they also present elevated amplitudes at high frequencies, these are not as high, either because they are not directly over the voids or because of the lateral deepening of the vaulted tombs ceilings.

Another interesting observation in Figure 5b is that the spatial variation of the elevated spectral amplitudes suggests both the existence of two different voids (lower high frequency amplitudes at the location of A2 compared to those to the left and right of it) and their different dimensions (stronger imprint for tomb 29 and for a larger distance, comparable to the length of its chamber, ~4m). This suggests that denser measurements could provide an even better description of the geometry of the voids as well as their separation.

Figure 5. a) Geophones (A1-A6) placement over the void chambers of tombs codenamed 28 and 29 in the Mycenaean Park of Voudeni. b) Spatial variability of the spectral amplitudes of the vertical component of ambient noise recordings. Black frames mark the interpreted imprints of the two voids in the form of elevated amplitudes at high frequencies.

Conclusions/Discussion

We have tested the H/V method for its ability to contribute to the detection of underground voids as suggested by Castellaro and Mulargia (2009), using as test targets the chambers of Mycenaean tombs of various sizes in the archaeological park of Voudeni in the Peloponnese. We performed single point measurements over the center of the chambers as well as linear arrays over selected chambers using both 3C and 1C geophones. We have shown that the detection and even mapping of the lateral extent of voids by the H/V method is feasible considering the persistent drop of the H/V curve below 1 at high frequencies (in our test cases generally >20Hz). We also showed a correlation between void size and the frequency above which the H/V curve drops below 1. By separately examining the spatial variation of the horizontal and vertical spectral amplitudes over the voids, we concluded that the H/V drop below 1 is mostly due to an amplification of the vertical component rather than a de-amplification of the horizontal. This motivated us to further investigate the potential of detecting subsurface voids based on array measurements with 1C, vertical sensors alone, and we concluded that such an approach is indeed feasible.

Of the 24 single point measurements of ambient noise that we made over voids, 17 of them showed the expected drop in the H/V curve at high frequencies. The reason why the method “failed” in some cases is not yet understood and requires theoretical modelling beyond the scope of this initial feasibility study. It should be noted that although our test site is ideal in terms of the variety of void target sizes, it is also very complicated due to the density and often close proximity of tombs of different sizes, as well as the different shapes of chamber roofs (pyramidal, hipped, vaulted, arched). This was partly demonstrated in the third phase of our measurements, where we measured along a line over two adjacent tombs of different sizes.

Contrary to the preferred interpretation of Castellaro and Mulargia (2009), our results suggest that the drop of the H/V curve below 1 over voids is mainly due to increased spectral amplitudes in the vertical component. This does not mean that the horizontal component is not de-amplified, as would be expected above such an extreme velocity reversal (void within rock), but

that the amplification of the vertical component is more distinct, localized, and easier to detect in terms of its spatial variation. A possible explanation for why the vertical component is amplified above a void was proposed by Kolesnikov and Fedin (2017), who studied an experimental model and proposed the occurrence of standing P waves between the ground surface and the top of the void. This implies a vertical amplification at higher frequencies for shallower voids compared to deeper ones.

In conclusion, our tests support the findings and suggestions of the work of Castellaro and Mulargia (2009) that the H/V curve has special characteristics over voids. This means that the H/V method could be used in the geophysical prospection of underground voids, at least as a complementary method to other more tested and robust methods. Considering that the method is gaining popularity due to its ease of use and cost-effectiveness, it is important for the community to further investigate this possible additional use for void detection, a very common need in geophysical exploration with diverse applications such as archaeological prospection, geological hazard assessment, and infrastructure monitoring.

Our work also suggests that linear array measurements of the vertical component alone may be equally useful. Such measurements are routinely performed by most research groups for site characterization with low-cost equipment, and only require some targeted additional processing to be useful for void detection.

It should be emphasized that, as with all geophysical methods, the interpretation of the results of the proposed methods outside the geological context of a studied site is insecure, and there is always the potential - if not the certainty - that multiple other factors influence the measurements. Several such factors are reviewed and discussed in detail in Castellaro and Mulargia (2009), particularly in relation to the topic discussed here. H/V results can be useful for void detection but should always be corroborated with other geophysical methods for accurate subsurface characterization.

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